

Sensible Signs of the Supersensible: On the Intellectual Interest in Natural Beauty

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I'll approach the fascinating theme of this conference from the standpoint of aesthetic experience, as developed in Kant's *Critique of the Power of Judgment*. My aim is to propose that the *sensible* has, in Kant's aesthetic theory, a distinctive and reflective meaning: it is not merely the realm of receptivity or appearance, but an *engagement* in which sensibility gestures beyond itself toward our moral and rational capacities. My aim is to demonstrate that such aesthetic significance of the sensible highlights its importance for the moral meaning of aesthetic experience.

To approach this claim, I want to begin by asking a 'simple' question: what is 'experience' in 'aesthetic experience' stands for? What is it that we experiencing in aesthetic experience? Is it the represented object or the activity of our cognitive faculties? and what are the empirical conditions that allow for the representation of certain objects in nature as beautiful?¹ (Perhaps these are not such simple questions after all..).

To answer, it is necessary to first comprehend Kant's stance towards nature within the aesthetic context.

One of Kant's well-known arguments regarding our aesthetic appreciation of nature is that beauty must be natural, or a product of nature: Kant stresses that it must be *nature*, or at least taken to be nature by us, that creates the beauty which pleases us.² But what does it mean to think of beauty as created by nature?

The main notion of 'nature' as it manifests in our aesthetic appreciation of nature, is the contrast between nature and man-made objects (artefacts). In contrast to an artificial product, which is

¹ The last question is slightly different and will not be discussed here at length, but it is also closely related to the principle of subjective purposiveness, as we see further, so I have included it here as well.

² CJ, 5:303.

created by humans for a specific end, nature must be considered *free* from any specific purpose to which it can be subjected and which it is supposed to serve.

Therefore, from this perspective, nature is considered as being in a state of *pure existence*, unbound by the constraints of (human) purposes. Nature produces its products freely, and this is what allows the harmony between its beautiful forms and our cognitive abilities (as we shall further see).

From *our* perspective, this means that when we make an aesthetic evaluation of beauty in nature, we should not project our own purposes onto nature but rather treat it as it is on a purely phenomenal level, as a ‘blind mechanism’, in Kant's words.³ The significance of this assertion lies in the premise that only when nature is experienced by us as free can our aesthetic appreciation of it be autonomous and lead to universally valid judgments of taste.

More specifically for the purpose of this talk, the significance of nature in its pure form, i.e., *as nature*, is closely linked to its moral significance. For only in relation to free nature can we have, what Kant calls, an *intellectual interest* in the actual existence of beautiful objects in nature, in a way similar to our interest in the existence or realization of the moral object (as we shall further see).

Kant illustrates this with few well known ‘fraud examples’. I’ll take the most generic one: He asks us to imagine a person who, alone in nature, contemplates some of its beautiful forms, with no interest in communicating their observations to others. This person, Kant says, takes pleasure not only in the *form* of nature’s products but also (and this is the crucial point for our theme) in their *existence*, even though no sensory charm plays a part in this and no purpose or end is combined with this pleasure.⁴

Yet, Kant continues the example, suppose that this person later discovers that everything they admired was, in fact, artificial, the work of human hands, not of nature. Kant says that in such a

³ CJ, 5:361.

⁴ CJ, 5:299.

case, the immediate interest they took in that beauty (with regard to its form and existence) would vanish.⁵

Why? Here we go back to the ‘beauty as a product of nature’ where Kant asserts that “*The thought that nature has produced that beauty must accompany the intuition and reflection, and on this alone is grounded the immediate interest that one takes in it.*”⁶

This straightforward example shows that aesthetic pleasure in natural beauty depends on a peculiar condition: we must experience it as if nature itself were the *source* of the form that pleases us. In other words, sensibility, here, is not passive reception; it is a *reflective activity* that attributes meaning and purposiveness to the sensible world. And this, I will argue, is the key to understanding how aesthetic experience becomes, for Kant, a *sensible sign of the supersensible*: an experience in which the sensible in its very *existence* or *factuality*, does not close us within appearances but opens us toward something that exceeds it: our moral vocation.

In order to get a better understanding of this transition from sensible nature to moral freedom (to use Kant’s own terms) I’d like to pause on the question of *existence*. What sort of *existence* is at stake in the aesthetic experience of nature?

This question is crucial, because judgments of taste, as Kant repeatedly emphasizes, are characterized by their *disinterestedness*: they are indifferent *precisely* to the empirical or rational desire for an object’s existence. When we judge something to be beautiful, we do not want to possess it, nor do we affirm its existence as a means to some further end. Stated differently, in judging natural beauty we take pleasure in the representation of the object regardless of whether its existence would be useful to us, and regardless of whether or not we are inclined to respond to the sensuous pleasure we get from its existence.

And yet, as we just saw, the pleasure in the beautiful forms of a wildflower, a bird, an insect (to use Kant’s examples) depends on the *thought* that their beautiful form truly *exists* as nature’s own

⁵ Another well-known example of a songbird, which we can listen to and enjoy endlessly, but as soon as we find out that this song actually belongs to someone who can imitate the bird’s song perfectly, our pleasure stops right away. (CJ, 5: 302)

⁶ CJ, 5:299.

product. When that thought collapses, (when we discover that what we took for nature is in fact human artifice) the pleasure collapses with it. The point is not that the artificial object ceases to exist, but that its existence no longer has the *kind* of reality that grounds aesthetic pleasure. It no longer counts, for us, as the kind of existence that can be disinterestedly affirmed.

The fraud examples (I want to suggest) therefore reveals a deeper tension at the heart of Kant's aesthetic theory: on the one hand, aesthetic judgment must be *disinterested* with respect to the object's existence; on the other hand, it seems to depend, quite essentially, on a certain *mode* of existence, one that is not merely empirical, but somehow meaningful to *us* as natural and, ultimately, moral beings.

Let us begin by unpacking the tension between being *disinterested* in the existence of an object, on the one hand, and Kant's turn toward the *intellectual* interest in the beauty of nature, which seems to imply a distinctive sense of existence: one in which we are, precisely, intellectually interested.

Interest, Existence, and the Turn Toward the Intellectual Interest

At the beginning of the *Critique of the Power of Judgment*, Kant describes interest (*Interesse*) in general as “the satisfaction that we combine with the representation of the existence [*der Existenz*] of an object”.⁷ In this broad sense, to take an interest in something is to desire that it exist, or to have pleasure in its existence. Interest thus presupposes a relation between pleasure and existence: we take pleasure not simply in an object's form or idea, but in its actuality.

This definition grounds the well-known distinction between *interested* and *disinterested* pleasure. Either if we have interest in something for its own sake, in that case our interest is pathological: we desire the existence of what pleases the senses. Or we have interest in the existence of what is useful for some other end, for example, our rational interest in the good. Against both of these, aesthetic pleasure is defined precisely by the absence of such interest. Aesthetic judgment, Kant

⁷ CJ, 5:204.

writes, is “merely contemplative, i.e., a judgment that [is] indifferent with regard to the existence of an object.”⁸

Notice, that the disinterestedness Kant describes concerns our interest in *external* objects, such as the existence of sensible objects in the agreeable or the realization of supersensible ideas in the case of pleasure in the morally good. By contrast, aesthetic judgment, Kant argues, is disinterested in the sense that it:

“contributes nothing to cognition but only holds the given representation in the subject up to the entire faculty of representation, of which *the mind becomes conscious in the feeling of its state*”.⁹

This reflective activity can be regarded as an object of interest because, although it does not concern the existence of an external object, it *does* concern the existence of the subject’s own mental state: one that bears on maintenance of the reflective activity internal to the judgment itself (the ongoing free play between imagination and understanding: of which “*the mind becomes conscious in the feeling of its state*”, which is the feeling of the subject’s awareness or consciousness to her life-enhancing character. Thus, by “the feeling of its state” Kant refers to the subject’s ‘feeling of life’).

The point for our purpose is that while the disinterestedness of aesthetic pleasure involves an indifference to the existence of the *object*, it at the same time increases the sense of the *subject’s* existence by furthering her feeling of being alive.¹⁰ This feeling constitutes a kind of *inner existence*, a sensibly given awareness of our own being (or *Dasein*). Hence even disinterested pleasure entails a distinctive relation to existence: not the existence of the object, but the existence of the subject’s mental state in free reflectivity (see: “what I make of this representation *in myself*”).

Seen in this light, the transition to the *intellectual* interest in natural beauty conforms much more organically to aesthetic disinterestedness: it appears as a deepening of the reflective interest already

⁸ CJ, 5:209.

⁹ CJ, 5:204. Emphasis mine.

¹⁰ Kant connects existence and perception, by defining *Existenz*, *Dasein*, and *Wirklichkeit* in terms of perception (*Wahrnehmung*). In aesthetic judgment, however, perception becomes a ‘reflected perception’: it not the intuition of an external object but the feeling of the harmony between our faculties, the “feeling of life” that accompanies free reflection. CJ, 5: 191. See also 5: 189, 236, 258.

implicit in aesthetic pleasure. Let us now turn, then, to §42, where Kant introduces this intellectual interest.

§42 On the Intellectual Interest in the Beautiful

Kant's main concern here (let's keep in mind that we are in the context of the 'Deduction of Pure Aesthetic Judgments') is the kind of interest that can be brought into a *universal* and *necessary* connection with the disinterested pleasure we take in the beautiful. The reason for this is that only such a connection (i.e., universal and necessary) would be capable of generating a *duty* to also take an interest in the existence of the beautiful object, and, as a result, to develop the aesthetic (human) capacity to appreciate its beauty.

The sense of existence Kant refers to here does not denote an empirical or desired existence (which aesthetic judgment must exclude!) but refers to a 'morally inflected mode of existence',¹¹ one that elicits not empirical inclination but a distinctive mode of *responsiveness* to the object.

There are 2 aspects to the intellectual interest in natural beauty that reflect this distinctive mode of responsiveness:

First, it concerns our mode of *approaching nature as moral beings*. Kant explicitly writes that "to take an immediate interest in the beauty of nature (not merely to have taste in order to judge it) is always a *mark* of a good soul."¹² This claim is crucial. It implies that in order to take an intellectual interest in natural beauty we must be morally oriented. That is, insofar as we are truly committed to our moral ends, we must assume that they are (at least in principle) realizable, and this involves interpreting nature as compatible with the realization of these ends.

Thus, a person with a good moral disposition who is striving to realize their moral ends (as they ought to do in Kant's moral view) will *necessarily* interpret any manifestation of nature's subjective formal purposiveness as an indication of nature's moral purposiveness and will take an intellectual interest in its beautiful forms.

¹¹ Akin to the notion of 'inner existence' or *Dasein* I referred to before.

¹² CJ, 5:299.

The second aspect brings us back to the “fraud example” with which I began: the person contemplating nature’s beauty who later discovers it was all an artificial construction. The interest that disappears in that moment is precisely the intellectual one. The intellectual interest therefore consists in caring about the existence of the object simply because of what it is: a product of nature, and not for any end that it might serve us. This means that when we take an intellectual interest in natural beauty we experience pleasure not only in the form of natural beautiful objects, but also in their very existence.

These two aspects taken together gives us the sense of how natural beauty serves as a sign of the supersensible. Since we feel in aesthetic experience of natural beauty as if nature *itself* is giving us signs, or hints to use Kants language (CJ, 5: 300), of its possible correspondence with our moral vocation. The intellectual interest in natural beauty arises, for Kant, when we come to see nature not merely as pleasing in form, but as providing a *hint (Wink)* of a deeper harmony (that we take in the *presence* of nature), one that resonates with our moral vocation.

Since nature’s beautiful forms gives us a hint of this harmony, through the idea of subjective formal purposiveness (that underlies this assumption), we take pleasure in their existence.

Similar to the pleasure we feel in the fact that nature in aesthetic experience is amenable to our cognitive ends and seems to satisfy our intellectual needs (that is expressed in what I previously called: ‘inner existence’), so too any hint, trace, or sign that nature is amenable to the realization of our practical ends and is in accord with our moral intentions is significant to us and will please us.

In this way, the intellectual interest completes and deepens the structure of existence implicit in disinterested pleasure. Earlier we saw that aesthetic experience, though indifferent to the object’s external existence, intensifies our awareness of our own inner existence: the feeling of life in which sensibility and reason are in harmony. The intellectual interest adds to this a further dimension: the affirmation of nature whose very existence seems to accord with that harmony.

Before moving to conclusion, I want to summaries the argument so far:

Up to this point I have approached the sensible in aesthetic experience by focusing on the notion of existence and the distinctive ways in which it becomes meaningful within aesthetic judgment.

1. I first showed that, although judgments of taste are formally disinterested in the existence of the object, they nevertheless disclose a mode of existence internal to the subject: the inner existence expressed in the feeling of life generated by the free play of the faculties. Aesthetic pleasure thus enhances our awareness of our own reflective activity.

2. I then argued that §42 introduces a further layer: the intellectual interest in natural beauty, which concerns a morally inflected form of existence. This interest responds to natural beauty as if it were a *sign* of a deeper harmony between the sensible world and our moral vocation.

3. In this way, aesthetic experience draws upon sensibility to reveal forms of existence that go beyond empirical nature: first inwardly, in the subject's feeling of life, and then outwardly, in the thought of nature's accord with our moral capacities.

Taken together, these steps show how aesthetic experience becomes an activity in which sensibility points beyond itself, toward our moral and rational capabilities. Here, arises implicitly the idea of cultivating aesthetic sensitivity by learning to pay attention to the signs and hints that nature presents (in its beautiful forms) to express our moral vocation.

In conclusion, I would like to propose a broader perspective and to draw upon the relationship between intellectual interest and the notion of humanity itself, as well as the implications of this connection for the aesthetic sense of the sensible I have drawn so far.

Conclusion: Aesthetic Experience and the Idea of Humanity

As I have discussed, in the *experience* of natural beauty, we feel that an object perfectly fits our faculties; it is *as if* nature's form were attuned to our cognitive constitution. This gives us 'a sign' (*Wink*) that nature "contains in itself some sort of ground for assuming a lawful correspondence of its products with our satisfaction that is independent of all interest" (CJ, 5:300).

Kant immediately goes on to argue that

“[R]eason must take an interest in every manifestation in nature of a correspondence similar to this; consequently the mind cannot reflect on the beauty of nature without finding

itself at the same time to be interested in it. Because of this *affinity*, however, this interest is moral” (CJ, 5: 300)

The idea is that natural beauty arouses an immediate interest in us [in those already morally predisposed] because there is an intimate “affinity” (*Verwandtschaft*) between our moral interest in the realization of our moral ends and the interest we take in any traces, signs or hints of nature’s harmony with those ends.

Insofar as nature’s beautiful forms actually gives us a hint of this harmony, we experience pleasure not merely in their form, but also in their very existence. Nonetheless, it is not the objective existence *per se*, but rather a distinctive, morally oriented mode of existence (the existence we care about because it resonates with practical reason’s final end).

Here we see how our aesthetic responsiveness to nature prepares us to regard ourselves as *beings* capable of moral vocation. Aesthetic judgment, though formally grounded in sensible nature, reveals a structure of human nature that is both finite and open to the supersensible. This is why Kant can say that “taste is at bottom a faculty for the judging of the sensible rendering [*Versinnlichung*] of moral ideas,” a faculty through which a form of pleasure arises that is “valid for mankind in general.”¹³

This is also why Kant claims that we have a *duty* to cultivate taste, which reflects the specific notion of existence that emerges within aesthetic experience. Disinterested pleasure, though “not itself moral”, is a disposition of sensibility that prepares us for morality (MM, 6: 443) because it refines our relation to our *own existence* independently of inclination.¹⁴

Hence Kant can say that human beings have an “end of ... existence” (MM, 6:445): which refers to a natural final end that concerns forming ourselves as beings capable of freely choosing which predispositions to develop. Such choice is not determined by theoretical understanding or by practical reason; it requires the reflective, non-determinative capacity exercised in aesthetic judgment. Thus, the mode of existence revealed in aesthetic experience grounds the human capacity for free self-formation.

¹³ CJ, 5:356.

¹⁴ explicitly to *feeling of life* (*Lebensgefühl*).

This, I propose, puts Kant's account of aesthetic experience as offering a unique understanding of the sensible: as a reflective mode of *engagement* in which we encounter nature as bearing a meaning whose existence we can take pleasure in precisely *as such*, that is, both disinterestedly and as satisfying our intellectual interest.

Kant captures the deeper significance of this shift when he writes that

“Only through that which [the human being] does ..., in full freedom and independently of what nature could passively provide for him, does he give his being [*Dasein*] as the existence [*Existenz*] of a person an absolute value” (CJ, 5:209).

In aesthetic judgment, the harmony of sensibility and rationality thus allows the subject's own state of reflection to acquire value. This means, peculiar as it may seem, that the *a priori* principle of subjective purposiveness has a sensible core.

Thus, the sensible proves to be a sign of the supersensible precisely because the reflective structure of aesthetic judgment discloses, within experience itself, the capacities through which we recognize our moral vocation.